

IMPROVING ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract: This article contains scientific opinions on further improvement of English language teaching in higher education institutions.

Key words: English language, innovation, methodology, teacher, skill, ability, educational program.

Currently, there are many areas that determine the bright future of our country and ensure its strength. The higher education system is undoubtedly of special importance among them. Because the future of our nation and people is closely related to the fate of young specialists who are receiving higher education today. From the first years of our country's independence, attention has been paid to the issue of reforming the education system at the level of state policy, to ensure that our young people receive education in conditions corresponding to world standards, to mature into physically and spiritually mature people, to bring out their abilities and talents, This noble goal is embodied in the heart of the incomparable efforts made to form feelings of loyalty and devotion to the country.

In our country, every year, several areas of science are selected and developed with special attention. In 2022, physics and foreign languages are defined as such priority areas in Uzbekistan. Uzbekistan's policy of openness, its active entry into the world market, and the expansion of international cooperation in all fields increase the need to know foreign languages. Today, teaching is conducted in foreign languages in 25 higher educational institutions of our country. In 2016, they were only 7. The number of graduates who received an international language certificate has increased 10 times in the last 3 years. In 2021, 350 students were awarded scholarships to study at prestigious foreign universities through the "El-Yurt Umid" fund. This is 5 times more than in previous years. Tashkent State University of World Languages and Oriental Studies, together with the Samarkand Institute of Foreign Languages, has a branch of foreign languages as a base university in each region.

The head of our state emphasized the need to create suitable conditions for teachers and encourage them, taking into account their qualifications. Teachers with international certificates of primary and secondary education will receive a 40% salary increase, and those who have achieved high results will receive a 50% salary increase. In addition, high-scoring teachers will be reimbursed for the cost of taking tests for international certification. Starting next year, new foreign language teachers will have to have national and international certificates. In the next three years, all 53,000 foreign language teachers in schools must obtain an international certificate. Using the created opportunities, the task was set to fill vacancies in schools with qualified specialists. 207 schools in districts and cities were selected for in-depth teaching of foreign languages. In these schools, foreign books, advanced educational programs and teaching methods, and teaching of subjects in a foreign language

will be free of charge. Regional governments were instructed to allocate 1 billion soums from the local budget to each district and city to improve the quality of teaching foreign languages in schools. It was emphasized the importance of attracting foreign teachers who speak this language to specialized schools and higher educational institutions, holding competitions in each district, and organizing foreign language teachers' internship abroad.

The quality of teaching also depends on textbooks and methodical manuals conforming to international standards. Therefore, the task of approving the English textbooks of the Cambridge University Publishing House in 200 schools and implementing them in all schools next year was set. He said that such works will be organized in Russian, German, Korean, Chinese and French languages. 1 million soums will be allocated from the budget to each foreign language teacher so that they can keep up with changes in the field, buy new literature and manuals. The Ministry of Preschool Education, in cooperation with UNICEF, has been assigned the task of developing and implementing a methodological guide on teaching foreign languages to children under 7 years of age. I believe that we, teachers, in order to ensure the performance of these tasks, should first of all fundamentally reform our educational and methodological materials and bring them to the level of perfect learning of foreign languages, including English, based on the requirements of today's times. For this, I believe that it is appropriate to abandon the old traditional methods of teaching, and to use new methods of teaching, such as memorizing by hearing, strengthening by speaking, and correcting pronunciation by speaking.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

It is known from the evidence presented above that today attention is paid to the issue of providing educational institutions with qualified foreign language teachers and training personnel with in-depth knowledge at the level of state policy. As we mentioned above, special requirements are placed on foreign language teachers in higher education institutions, and they are required to have an appropriate certificate in order to work as a foreign language teacher. In addition, it is required to have a certificate of knowledge of one of the foreign languages in order to enter the master's degree, which is considered the second stage of higher education, and the doctorate, which is considered post-higher education. In addition, it is mandatory for professors of higher education institutions to know foreign languages. In addition, it has been established that after the specified period, specialized subjects in higher education institutions will also be conducted in foreign languages. It can be seen that special importance is attached to teaching foreign languages, including English, in higher education institutions. We believe that it is appropriate to implement the following in order to ensure the implementation of these specified tasks, to bring the teaching of foreign languages, including English, up to date in higher education institutions, and to improve students' learning of foreign languages.

It would be appropriate to carry out an inventory of the material and technical bases of higher education institutions for teaching foreign languages, including English, with the help of experienced specialists..

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